

Quasiperiodic Dynamics in a Large Chain of Pump-Coupled Lasers

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(Received 20 November, 2024)

We study the conditions for quasiperiodic dynamics in a chain of a large number of diffusively coupled lasers on the base of the distributed integro-differential model. The model takes into account the delay due to the optoelectronic conversion of signals in pumping lines. The values of coupling coefficient and the delay time are determined at which the codimension-two bifurcation of the stationary state occurs. A system of two complex Ginzburg–Landau equations is obtained as a quasi-normal form in the neighborhood of the bifurcation point. We get the homogeneous solutions of the quasi-normal which correspond to inhomogeneous waves in the distributed model. Such solutions can be interpreted as two- or three-frequency antiphase regimes in the chain of coupled lasers.

PACS numbers: 42.65.Hw, 42.25.Fx, 42.62.Be

Keywords: laser dynamics, delayed differential equations, bifurcation analysis, wave structures

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15081335>

1. Introduction

Networks of coupled lasers are actively studied due to promising applications in photonics [1]. The dynamics of a small number of coupled lasers have been investigated in most detail. Complete or localized synchronization, suppressing oscillations as well as dynamic chaos were observed in models of two coupled lasers [2–6]. Of the particular interest is the influence of delay in coupling circuits on the dynamics. There were reported on delay-induced oscillation death, multistability of synchronous modes, the formation of traveling waves, cluster states in a ring of oscillators [7–10]. Also, keeping in mind the purpose of this article, we note a quasi-periodic scenario of transition to chaos in delayed coupled laser systems [11–13].

Instabilities of radiation in a large chain

of lasers were studied in models for different design of coupling circuits [14–16]. In the case of unidirectional couplings, the critical value of coupling coefficient was obtained to be delay-independent while the phase difference of adjacent oscillators is determined by the delay [14, 15]. In the case of bidirectional coupling design, oppositely, delay-dependent critical coupling values were determined [16]. It was shown that due to bifurcation the set of modes with different frequency are exited at different intervals of the delay. That can lead, at some intervals of the delay, in antiphase or in-phase oscillations in a chain of lasers.

The aim of this paper is to study the conditions for a codimension-two bifurcation when both sets of modes with different frequencies are exited. Also, we derive the quasi-normal form in a small neighborhood of such bifurcation points and analyze its homogeneous solutions.

The material of the article is presented as follows. In Section 2 we discuss the model of

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a closed chain (a ring) of lasers with diffusion-like couplings through pumping circuits. The number of lasers in the chain is assumed to be large. A distributed integro-differential model with a small parameter inversely proportional to the number of lasers in the chain is proposed. Section 3 presents the results of the stability analysis of the equilibrium state of the distributed model. The bifurcation values of the coupling coefficient, frequencies and wave numbers of the emerging traveling waves in the linearized system are obtained. It is shown that when a small parameter tends to zero, the dimension of the critical case tends to infinity. In section 4, following the methods presented in [17], solutions of a nonlinear system are constructed in neighborhood of codimension-two bifurcations. For the amplitude of the main terms of the expansion, a system of boundary value problems with periodic boundary conditions is obtained. These equations take the role of quasi-normal form which determines solutions to the original nonlinear system for a large number of coupled lasers. In section 5, the homogeneous solutions of the quasi-normal form are obtained. We show that corresponding solutions of the original model can be interpreted as one-, two- and three-frequency anti-phase oscillations in a large chain of lasers.

2. Model of diffusively coupled lasers

Consider a closed chain of N lasers. Let the coupling between lasers be realized by optoelectronic means so that the pumping rate of each laser depends, with a delay, on the difference in the radiation densities of two adjacent elements of the chain and the element itself. The dynamical model can be based on the standard rate equations for the photon density $u_j(t)$ and the population inversion of the active medium $y_j(t)$ in a two-level approximation takes the form,

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{u}_j &= v u_j (y_j - 1), \\ \dot{y}_j &= q - y_j (1 + u_j) - \Phi_{j,j\pm 1}, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $j = 1, 2, \dots$ is the laser number in the chain, the dot denotes the derivative of the functions with respect to time t , which is normalized to the relaxation time of the population inversion; v is the ratio of the photon decay rate in the resonator to the population relaxation rate; the resonator loss is normalized to unity, q is the normalized pumping rate and here we set $q > 1$. The coupling function reads

$$\Phi_{j,j\pm 1} = \frac{\gamma}{4} [u_{j+1}(t-T) + u_{j-1}(t-T) - 2u_j(t-T)]$$

where the parameters γ and T have the meaning of the coupling coefficient and the delay time in the coupling line, respectively, the identities

$$u_{j+N} \equiv u_j, \quad y_{j+N} \equiv y_j$$

are valid for a ring (a closed chain). We call such a connection a diffusion-type coupling, bearing in mind the analogy with the discrete representation of the diffusion operator. Also, we limit ourselves to the values $\gamma > 0$ and use the $1/4$ multiplier to simplify further calculations.

Let the chain consists of a sufficiently large number of elements, $N \gg 1$. Then we can introduce the parameter $\varepsilon = 2\pi N^{-1}$ and

$$0 < \varepsilon \ll 1. \quad (2)$$

The parameter ε can be interpreted as the angular distance between lasers in a ring of length 2π . Then the values of the functions $u_j(t)$, $y_j(t)$ can be associated with the values of the functions of two variables $u(t, x)$, $y(t, x)$, respectively, at points $x = x_j = \varepsilon j$. Condition (2) gives reasons to move from the system (1) containing $2N$ equations by the system of two equations for spatially distributed functions $u(t, x)$, $y(t, x)$,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} &= v u (y - 1), \\ \frac{\partial y}{\partial t} &= q - y (1 + u) \\ &\quad - \gamma \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F(s) u(t - T, x + s) ds, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

with periodic boundary conditions

$$u(t, x + 2\pi) \equiv u(t, x), \quad y(t, x + 2\pi) \equiv y(t, x), \quad (4)$$

where the function $F(s)$ is composed of Gaussian functions with parameters ε and ς ,

$$\begin{aligned} F(s) &= \frac{1}{4}(F_+(s) + F_-(s) - 2F_0(s)), \\ F_{\pm}(s) &= \frac{1}{\varsigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{(s \pm \varepsilon)^2}{2\varsigma^2}\right), \\ F_0(s) &= \frac{1}{\varsigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{s^2}{2\varsigma^2}\right). \end{aligned}$$

The function $F(s)$ models a diffusion-type coupling, since the asymptotic equality

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F(s)W(x+s)ds \\ &= \frac{1}{4}\left(W(x+\varepsilon) + W(x-\varepsilon) - 2W(x)\right) + o(1) \end{aligned}$$

holds for any continuous function $W(x)$ and $\varsigma \rightarrow 0$. Then the integral term in the equation (3) describes the connection between the elements of the ring, in which the pumping rate of the element at point x depends most strongly on the difference in the radiation densities of the two elements at points $x \pm \varepsilon$ and at point x , and the strength of the coupling between other elements of the ring decreases exponentially with increasing distance between them. The ς parameter characterizes the width of the spatial region of effective interaction of elements. The continuous model will be most adequate to the discrete chain model if the area of interaction between the elements is significantly smaller than the distance ε between them, therefore in this work we will put

$$\varsigma = \varepsilon^2\sigma \ll 1. \quad (5)$$

Next we study the solutions of the integro-differential system (3), (4) with small parameters (3) and (5) in infinite-dimensional phase space $C_{[0,2\pi]}(R^2) \times C_{[-T,0]}(R^2)$.

3. Stability of equilibrium state

The system (3), (4) at $q > 1$ has the homogeneous nonzero equilibrium state $u(x, t) \equiv u_s, y(x, t) \equiv y_s$, where

$$u_s = q - 1, \quad y_s = 1. \quad (6)$$

The local dynamics of the boundary value problem (3), (4) in the vicinity of the zero equilibrium state is mainly determined by the behavior of solutions of the linearized system. We look the solutions of the linearized system in the form $u, y \sim \exp(ikx + \lambda_k t)$, $k = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$ taking into account periodic boundary conditions.

3.1. Characteristic equation

To find the values of $\lambda = \lambda_k$ we obtain the characteristic equation

$$\lambda^2 + (1 + u_s)\lambda + vu_s[1 + \gamma g(z)e^{-\lambda T}] = 0, \quad (7)$$

where $z = \varepsilon k$,

$$\begin{aligned} g(z) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F(s) \exp(iks) ds \\ &= -\sin^2\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \exp\left(-z^2 \frac{\varepsilon^2 \sigma^2}{2}\right). \end{aligned}$$

It is important that the function $g(z)$ takes the maximum absolute value $|g(z)| = 1$ for $z = z_n = \pi + 2\pi n$, $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ and $\sigma \rightarrow 0$.

Remark 1. Eq. (7) coincides with the characteristic equation for the model of a single laser with delayed feedback, if $\Gamma = \gamma g(z)$ is considered as the feedback coefficient.

The following general statements are true.

Statement 1. Let for all $z \in (-\infty, \infty)$ all the roots of the equation (7) have negative real parts. Then all solutions of the linearized boundary value problem with initial conditions from some sufficiently small and ε -independent neighborhood, the zero equilibrium state tends to zero at $t \rightarrow \infty$.

Under this condition, the problem of the local dynamics of the nonlinear problem (3), (4) is trivial.

Statement 2. *Let there be such a z_0 that for $z = z_0$ the equation (7) has a root with a positive real part. Then for all sufficiently small ε , the null solution in the linearized boundary value problem is unstable and there are no attractors of this boundary value problem in its small neighborhood.*

In the condition of this statement, the problem of the dynamics of the system (3), (4) becomes non-local.

3.2. Critical case at $\sigma = 0$

Let the characteristic equation (7) for $\sigma = 0$, $\gamma = \gamma_0$ and $z = z_0$ has a root $\lambda = i\omega$ with zero real part and, for other $z \in (-\infty, \infty)$, characteristic roots have a negative real part. In such a critical case we obtain the characteristic frequency $\omega = \omega_J(\Gamma)$, $J = 1, 2$ and the characteristic phase $\varphi_J(\Gamma)$,

$$(\omega_J)^2 = \left[vu_s - \frac{(1 + u_s)^2}{2} \right] \pm \sqrt{D}, \quad (8)$$

$$D = \frac{(1 + u_s)^4}{4} - vu_s(1 + u_s)^2 + (vu_s)^2 \Gamma^2,$$

$$\varphi_J = \omega_J T = \arctan \frac{\omega_J(1 + u_s)}{\omega_J^2 - vu_s}, \quad (9)$$

where subscript $J = 1$ ($J = 2$) correspond to the sign “+” (“−”) in front of the root of the discriminant D , $\Gamma = \gamma g(z)$. Each value of Γ corresponds to a set of values T_{Jl} with the indices $J = 1, 2$ and $l = 0, 1, \dots$ due to the periodicity of the tangent function,

$$T_{Jl} = \omega_J^{-1} [\varphi_J + 2\pi l + \pi(2 - J)], \quad (10)$$

Finally, considering the values of the inverse multivalued function $\Gamma(T)$ for a fixed value of T , we choose the smallest positive value Γ_0 . Since $|\Gamma| = \gamma \sin^2(z/2)$, then the smallest (critical) value of the coupling coefficient $|\gamma_0|$ is achieved at $z = z_n = \pi + 2\pi n$, $n = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$

FIG. 1. Bifurcation value γ_0 as a function of delay T for the chain model (3) with parameters $v = 1000$, $q = 1.5$, $\sigma = 0$ and $z = \pi$. From each local extremum point (for example, B and D), two branches of the bifurcation curve depart, corresponding to the excitation of modes with frequency ω_1 or ω_2 . The sections of the curve marked with black **circles** (*dots*) indicate the parameters corresponding to the **super**(*sub*)critical bifurcation, as a result of which a **stable** (*unstable*) traveling wave arises. Stable **anti-phase** oscillations in a laser chain are expected at parameters corresponding to the boundary sections (for example, to AB) formed by black **circles**.

In Fig. 1 we show the results of calculating the bifurcation values of the coupling coefficient γ_0 depending on the delay T using formulas (8) – (10) at $\sigma = 0$ and $z_0 = \pi$, $v = 1000$, $q = 1.5$. The stability boundary of the equilibrium state consists of many branches corresponding to indices $J = 1, 2$ and $l = 0, 1, 2, 3$ in the formula (10). Local minima of positive γ_0 -values are determined by the equality $\omega_1 = \omega_2$. From each local extremum point (B and D), two branches of the bifurcation curve depart, corresponding to the excitation of modes with frequency ω_1 (the boundary sections AB and CD) or ω_2 (the boundary sections BC and DG).

Remark 2. *We can simplify the formulas (8), (9) for the critical values of the parameters, taking into account that the parameter v for solid-state lasers has rather large values, $v \sim 10^2, \dots, 10^5 \gg 1$, and v determines the relaxation frequency $\omega_R =$*

$\sqrt{v(q-1)} \gg 1$ of a single laser. Then

$$\begin{aligned}\omega_{1,2} &= \omega_R \sqrt{1 \pm \gamma_0} (1 \mp O(v^{-1})), \\ \varphi_{1,2} &= \pm \frac{q}{\omega_R} \frac{\sqrt{1 \pm \gamma_0}}{\gamma_0} (1 \mp O(v^{-1})).\end{aligned}\quad (11)$$

Thus the frequencies of the excited modes are comparable to the relaxation frequency ω_R of a single laser.

Fig. 1 is made for $z = z_0 = \pi$. The same γ_0 values occur for any critical value $z = z_n = \pi + 2\pi n$, $n = 1, 2, \dots$. Each z_n determine the central value of wave numbers $k_{mn} = z_n \varepsilon^{-1} + m$, $m = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$ of those modes of the form $\exp(ik_{mn}x + i\omega_0 t)$, which are excited when the stationary state loses stability. All wave numbers of excited modes form the set

$$K = \{ \pi \varepsilon^{-1} + \theta + 2\pi n \varepsilon^{-1} + m, \\ n, m = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots \}, \quad (12)$$

where the correction $\theta = \theta(\varepsilon) \in [0, 1)$ completes the value $\pi \varepsilon^{-1}$ to an integer in order to provide periodic boundary conditions. Recall that $2\pi n \varepsilon^{-1} = Nn$ are integer since $\varepsilon = 2\pi N^{-1}$, and, therefore, $\theta = 1/2$ ($\theta = 0$) if the number of lasers in the chain N is odd (even).

Remark 3. *In the model of diffusively coupled lasers under consideration, the critical coupling level γ_0 depends on the delay T while the critical wave numbers from the set K do not depend on T . On the contrary, in the model with unidirectional coupling studied in [15], the critical value $\gamma_0 = \pm q(v(q-1))^{-1/2}(1 + O(v^{-1}))$ does not depend on the delay while the center wave number of the excited modes is determined by T .*

3.3. Critical case at $\sigma \neq 0$

We now obtain an asymptotic representation of the roots of the characteristic equation taking

into account (i) $\sigma \neq 0$, (ii) the correction θ for wave numbers k_{mn} from the set of integers K and (iii) the small deviation of the coupling parameters from critical values γ_0 , T_0 by an amount of the order of ε^2 , i.e. let us put in Eq. (7)

$$\gamma = \gamma_0 + \varepsilon^2 \gamma_{01}, \quad T = T_0 + \varepsilon^2 T_{01}. \quad (13)$$

For those roots $\lambda = \lambda_{mn}(\varepsilon)$, $n, m = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$, whose real parts tend to zero as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, the asymptotic equality is fulfilled:

$$\lambda_{mn} = i\omega_0 + \varepsilon \lambda_{mn1} + \varepsilon^2 \lambda_{mn2} + O(\varepsilon^3), \quad (14)$$

where $\omega_0 = \omega_1$ or $\omega_0 = \omega_2$ depending on the delay T_0 , $\lambda_{mn1} = 0$,

$$\lambda_{mn2} = \delta \left[\frac{\gamma_{01}}{\gamma_0} - i\omega_0 T_{01} - \frac{(\theta + m)^2}{4} - \frac{\sigma^2 \pi^2 (1 + 2n)^2}{2} \right], \quad (15)$$

$$\delta = \frac{\gamma_0 v u_s e^{-i\omega_0 T_0}}{2i\omega_0 + 1 + u_s + \gamma_0 v u_s T_0 e^{-i\omega_0 T_0}} \quad (16)$$

and $\Re \delta > 0$ is valid. Further we will use $\delta = \delta_{1,2}$ if $\omega_0 = \omega_1$ or $\omega_0 = \omega_2$ depending on the delay T_0 .

It follows from the series (14) that the characteristic equation (7) has infinitely many roots, the real parts of which tend to zero if $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$. Thus, the critical case under consideration has (asymptotically) infinite dimension or, in other words, infinitely many modes are excited at above-critical γ and T .

3.4. Codimension two bifurcation

Codimension two bifurcation takes place at the time delay values corresponding to the points of intersection of ω_1 - and ω_2 -bifurcation branches. Setting $T_{1l} = T_{2l}$, $l = 1, 2, \dots$, in Eq. (10) we conclude that there is a counter set of such points for which the equality

$$\frac{\varphi_1 + 2\pi l + \pi}{\omega_1} = \frac{\varphi_2 + 2\pi l}{\omega_2} \quad (17)$$

determines corresponding T_0 and γ_0 .

In Fig. 1, for example, such points are marked by C and G . The sets of modes with the frequency $\omega_1 = 26.0$ and $\omega_2 = 17.93$ are excited at $T_C = 0.362$, $\gamma_C = 0.42$. The modes with the frequency $\omega_1 = 25.0$ and $\omega_2 = 19.28$ are excited at $T_G = 0.64$, $\gamma_G = 0.263$.

Below we derive the quasi-normal form in some small neighborhood of such a bifurcation point, i.e. for $\gamma = \gamma_0 + \varepsilon^2\gamma_{01}$, $T = T_0 + \varepsilon^2T_{01}$, where $\varepsilon^2\gamma_{01}$ and ε^2T_{01} characterize the deviations from the bifurcation point (γ_0, T_0) .

4. Quasi-normal form

To each characteristic root $\lambda_{mn}(\varepsilon)$ there corresponds a particular solution of the linearized system. The frequency of each mode with wave number k_{mn} is defined as the imaginary part of the root λ_{mn} , given by the series (14) in powers of the small parameter ε . The leading terms of the series $i\omega_{1,2}$ are the same for all excited modes while differences appears in the second-order terms. This makes it possible to represent the general solution of the linearized system as a sum of carrier waves with an amplitude depending on spatial variables. Indeed, the general solution $u(t, x)$, $y(t, x)$ to the linear boundary value problem is the set of partial solutions, which can be written taking into account the decomposition of the characteristic roots in the following form,

$$\begin{pmatrix} u \\ y \end{pmatrix} = e^{iR_1} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ r_1 \end{pmatrix} \xi + e^{iR_2} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ r_2 \end{pmatrix} \eta, \quad (18)$$

where $R_{1,2} = k_{00}x + \omega_{1,2}t$ are the running variables, $k_{00} = \pi\varepsilon^{-1} + \theta$ is the central wave number, $\omega_{1,2}$ are the main frequencies, $r_{1,2} = i\omega_{1,2}(vu_s)^{-1}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \xi &= \sum_{m,n=-\infty}^{\infty} \xi_{mn} e^{(imX+inY+O(\varepsilon^2)t)} \\ \eta &= \sum_{m,n=-\infty}^{\infty} \eta_{mn} e^{(imX+inY+O(\varepsilon^2)t)}, \end{aligned}$$

ξ_{mn} , η_{mn} are some constants determined by the initial conditions, $X = x$ and $Y = 2\pi\varepsilon^{-1}x$ are

spatial variables. Note that the infinite sums ξ and η in Eqs. (18) can be viewed as the Fourier expansion of some functions $\xi(X, Y)$ and $\eta(X, Y)$ which are 2π -periodic in both spatial variables if we neglect the terms $O(\varepsilon^2)t$.

In order to construct the solution to the nonlinear boundary value problem (3), (4) we use the solution (18) of the linearized system and assume that the amplitudes of modes ξ_{mn} and η_{mn} change slowly with time. Then we introduce the functions $\xi(\tau, X, Y)$, $\eta(\tau, X, Y)$ which depend on the slow time variable $\tau = \varepsilon^2t$ and which are 2π -periodic on the spatial variables X, Y . The solution $u(t, x, \tau, X, Y)$ and $y(t, x, \tau, X, Y)$ of the nonlinear boundary value problem (3), (4) is represented as a formal series in powers of ε :

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ y \end{pmatrix} &= \varepsilon \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ r_1 \end{pmatrix} \xi e^{iR_1} + \varepsilon \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ r_2 \end{pmatrix} \eta e^{iR_2} \\ &+ \varepsilon^2 \begin{pmatrix} u_2 \\ y_2 \end{pmatrix} + \varepsilon^3 \begin{pmatrix} u_3 \\ y_3 \end{pmatrix} + O(\varepsilon^4) + c.c. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Here the functions

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon^2 u_2 &= \varepsilon^2 (u_{20} + u_{21} e^{i2R_1} + u_{22} e^{i2R_2} \\ &+ u_{23} e^{i(R_1+R_2)} + u_{24} e^{i(R_1-R_2)} + c.c.), \\ \varepsilon^2 y_2 &= \varepsilon^2 (y_{20} + u_{21} e^{i2R_1} + y_{22} e^{i2R_2} \\ &+ y_{23} e^{i(R_1+R_2)} + y_{24} e^{i(R_1-R_2)} + c.c.), \\ \varepsilon^3 u_3 &= \varepsilon^3 (u_{31} e^{iR_1} + u_{32} e^{iR_2} + \dots + c.c.), \dots \end{aligned}$$

denote values of the 2nd, 3rd, ... order in powers of ε . The functions $u_{20}(\tau, X, Y)$, $y_{20}(\tau, X, Y)$, $u_{22}(\tau, X, Y)$... are amplitudes harmonics of the fundamental frequency. All harmonic amplitudes, like $\xi(\tau, X, Y)$, slowly depend on time and are 2π -periodic on the spatial variables X, Y .

Let us substitute the series (19) into the nonlinear system (3) at $\gamma = \gamma_0 + \varepsilon^2\gamma_{01}$, $T = T_0 + \varepsilon^2T_{01}$ and collect the coefficients at the same powers of ε and harmonics of the fundamental frequency. Then we obtain the equalities from

which we find successively the slow amplitudes,

$$\begin{aligned} u_{20} &= 0, \quad y_{20} = 0, \\ u_{21} &= \frac{r_1}{u_s} C_1 \xi^2, \quad y_{21} = \frac{r_1}{u_s} (2r_1 C_1 - 1) \xi^2, \\ u_{22} &= \frac{r_2}{u_s} C_2 \eta^2, \quad y_{22} = \frac{r_2}{u_s} (2r_2 C_2 - 1) \eta^2, \\ u_{23} &= \frac{r_3}{u_s} C_3 \xi \eta, \quad y_{23} = \frac{r_3}{u_s} [r_3 C_3 - 1] \xi \eta, \\ u_{24} &= \frac{r_4}{u_s} C_4 \xi \eta^*, \quad y_{24} = \frac{r_4}{u_s} [r_4 C_4 - 1] \xi \eta^*, \end{aligned}$$

where $r_{1,2} = i\omega_{1,2}(vu_s)^{-1}$, $r_3 = r_1 + r_2$, $r_4 = r_1 - r_2$, $\omega_3 = \omega_1 + \omega_2$, $\omega_4 = \omega_1 - \omega_2$ and

$$\begin{aligned} C_{1,2} &= \frac{2i\omega_{1,2} + 1}{2r_{1,2}(i2\omega_{1,2} + 1 + u_s) + 1 + \gamma_0 e^{-i2\omega_{1,2}T_0}}, \\ C_{3,4} &= \frac{i\omega_{3,4} + 1}{r_{3,4}[i\omega_{3,4} + 1 + u_s] + 1 + \gamma_0 e^{-i\omega_{3,4}T_0}}. \end{aligned}$$

For the system to be solvable with respect to the amplitudes u_{31} , y_{31} , the existence condition must be satisfied, which leads to the system of equations for the complex functions $\xi(\tau, X, Y)$ and $\eta(\tau, X, Y)$,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \tau} &= \alpha_1 \xi + L_1 \xi (|\xi|^2 + 2|\eta|^2) \\ &+ \begin{pmatrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \end{pmatrix} \nabla \xi + \begin{pmatrix} D_1 \\ D_2 \end{pmatrix} \Delta \xi, \\ \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial \tau} &= \alpha_2 \xi + L_2 \eta (|\eta|^2 + 2|\xi|^2) \\ &+ \begin{pmatrix} v_3 \\ v_4 \end{pmatrix} \nabla \eta + \begin{pmatrix} D_3 \\ D_4 \end{pmatrix} \Delta \eta, \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

with 2π -periodic boundary conditions on both spatial arguments X and Y ,

$$\begin{aligned} \xi(X, Y) &= \xi(X + 2\pi, Y), \quad \xi(X, Y) = \xi(X, Y + 2\pi), \\ \eta(X, Y) &= \eta(X + 2\pi, Y), \quad \eta(X, Y) = \eta(X, Y + 2\pi). \end{aligned}$$

Here we use the operators $\nabla = (\partial/\partial X, \partial/\partial Y)$, $\Delta = (\partial^2/\partial X^2, \partial^2/\partial Y^2)$, and we denote the coefficients as

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{1,2} &= \delta_{1,2} \left(\frac{\gamma_{01}}{\gamma_0} - i\omega_{1,2}T_{01} - \frac{\theta^2}{4} - \frac{\sigma^2\pi^2}{2} \right), \\ L_{1,2} &= \frac{i\omega_{1,2}(i\omega_{1,2} + 1)(r_{1,2}C_{1,2} - 1)}{u_s^2(2i\omega_{1,2} + 1 + u_s + \gamma_0 vu_s T_0 e^{-i\omega_{1,2}T_0})}, \\ v_{1,3} &= -i\delta_{1,2}\theta/2, \quad v_{2,4} = -2i\delta_{1,2}\sigma^2\pi^2, \\ D_{1,3} &= \delta_{1,2}/4, \quad D_{2,4} = \delta_{1,2}\sigma^2\pi^2, \end{aligned}$$

$\delta_{1,2} = \delta(\omega_{1,2})$, and δ is defined in Eqs. (16).

We call the boundary value problem (20), a quasi-normal form, because it plays the role of a normal form: its nonlocal dynamics determines, for sufficiently small ε , the behavior of all solutions of the nonlinear system (3),(4) with initial conditions from some sufficiently small and ε -independent neighborhood of the zero equilibrium state. By the very construction of the boundary value problem (20), the relation between its solutions and the solutions of the original system follows, which is established by the following theorem.

Theorem 1. *Let the boundary value problem (20), has a solution $\xi_0(\tau, X, Y)$, $\eta_0(\tau, X, Y)$ bounded for $\tau \rightarrow \infty$ and for all $X \in (0, 2\pi]$, $Y \in (0, 2\pi]$. Then the boundary value problem (3), (4) at $\gamma = \gamma_0 + \varepsilon^2\gamma_{01}$, $T = T_0 + \varepsilon^2T_{01}$ has the solution*

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{pmatrix} u(t, x) \\ y(t, x) \end{pmatrix} &= \varepsilon \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ r_1 \end{pmatrix} \xi_0(\varepsilon^2 t, x, 2\pi\varepsilon^{-1}x) e^{iR_1} \\ &+ \varepsilon \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ r_2 \end{pmatrix} \eta_0(\varepsilon^2 t, x, 2\pi\varepsilon^{-1}x) e^{iR_2} + c.c. \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

that is asymptotic in the residual up to $O(\varepsilon^2)$.

5. On some solutions of the normal form

Let us consider simplest homogeneous in space solutions of the quasi-normal form (20) at typical laser parameter values. If $\xi(\tau, X, Y) = \xi(\tau)$ and $\eta(\tau, X, Y) = \eta(\tau)$, then all terms of Eqs. (20) containing spatial derivatives of ξ , η are equal to zero. The normal system reads,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \tau} &= \alpha_1 \xi + L_1 \xi (|\xi|^2 + 2|\eta|^2), \\ \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial \tau} &= \alpha_2 \xi + L_2 \eta (|\eta|^2 + 2|\xi|^2). \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

The normal form (22) has been studied in details, for example, in [18, 19]. Below we apply some their results to the problem Eqs. (22) with

coefficients corresponding to Eqs. (20) obtained above for the model of a large chain of lasers.

Let us denote

$$b_{1,2} = \Re L_{1,2}, \quad a_{1,2} = \Re \alpha_{1,2}. \quad (23)$$

The $b_{1,2}$ values determine the direction of the bifurcation. The bifurcation is supercritical for ω_1 -modes since $b_1 < 0$. The corresponding boundary is marked by black circles in Fig. 1. For ω_2 -modes, otherwise, the bifurcation appears to be subcritical since $b_2 > 0$. That is marked by dots in Fig. 1. Branches with different bifurcation direction intersect at the bifurcation points of codimension two, as can be seen from Fig. 1.

Remark 4. *Alternation of different bifurcation direction along the instability boundary is a special case. This phenomenon can be observed at sufficiently large values of the parameters T and $v \gg 1$ which are typical for class B lasers.*

In particular, we use $v = 10^3$ which is typical for semiconductor lasers in order to get stability boundary in Fig. 1.

The $a_{1,2}$ values are determined by parameter deviations γ_{01}, T_{01} from the critical point (γ_0, T_0) ,

$$\gamma - \gamma_0 = \varepsilon \gamma_{01}, \quad T - T_0 = \varepsilon T_{01}.$$

If $a_1 > 0$ ($a_2 < 0$), the system is in above (below) critical region. Choosing γ_{01}, T_{01} we can get into different sectors of the bifurcation diagram with the center at point of codimension-two bifurcation.

Fragment of the bifurcation diagram in neighborhood of the codimension-two bifurcation point is shown in Fig. 2. The central point G is the intersection point of two bifurcation branches corresponding to excitation modes with frequencies ω_1 and ω_2 . These branches are marked by black circles and by dots, correspondingly. It is possible to identify parameter sectors corresponding to different phase portraits for the degenerate vector fields. Points 1 – 4 mark parameters γ, T at which four types of solutions to Eqs. (3) are expected.

FIG. 2. Fragment of the bifurcation diagram presented in Fig. 1 in neighborhood of point G which is the intersection point of two bifurcation branches corresponding to excitation modes with frequencies ω_1 (black circles) and ω_2 (dots). Points 1 – 4 mark parameters γ, T at which the following solutions to Eqs. (3) are expected: 1 – stable ω_1 -waves given by Eq. (26); 2 – unstable ω_2 -oscillations given by Eq. (28); 3 – stable two-frequencies quasi-periodic oscillations given by Eq. (32); 4 – three-frequencies quasi-periodic oscillations given by Eq. (35).

Indeed, it was shown in [18, 19] that the normal form (22) can have following solutions.

1) The first solution of Eqs. (22) reads

$$\xi_{01}(\tau) = \rho_1 e^{i\omega_{11}\tau}, \quad \eta_{01}(\tau) = 0, \quad (24)$$

where

$$\rho_1 = \sqrt{\frac{a_1}{-b_1}}, \quad \omega_{11} = \Im m \alpha_1 + \rho_1^2 \Im m L_1.$$

Since $b_1 < 0$, this solution exists and is stable in the sector bounded by inequalities

$$a_1 > 0, \quad a_2 < -\frac{a_1}{2}. \quad (25)$$

For example, such a solution exist at the parameters corresponding point 1 in Fig. 2.

As it follows from Theorem 1, to the function (23) there corresponds the traveling wave solution of the boundary value problem (3), (4),

$$u(t, x) = 2\varepsilon \rho_1 \cos(\kappa x + \Omega t) + O(\varepsilon^2),$$

$$y(t, x) = 2\varepsilon \frac{\omega_1}{v u_s} \rho_1 \sin(\kappa x + \Omega t) + O(\varepsilon^2), \quad (26)$$

with frequency $\Omega = \omega_1 + \varepsilon^2 \omega_{11}$, and wave number $\kappa = k_{00} \varepsilon^{-1} + \theta$.

Such a traveling wave, in turn, can be associated with oscillations of the radiation intensity of coupled lasers located at points $x = x_j = \varepsilon j$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, N$ on the ring, $u_j(t) = u(t, x_j)$,

$$u_j(t) = 2\varepsilon \rho_1 \cos(\varepsilon \kappa j + \Omega t) + O(\varepsilon^2), \quad (27)$$

The oscillation phase shift for neighboring elements on the ring is equal to $\Delta\varphi = \varepsilon \kappa$. For the system (1), modeling chains with diffusion couplings, we obtain

$$\Delta\varphi = \begin{cases} \pi + \varepsilon/2, & \text{if } N \text{ is odd,} \\ \pi, & \text{if } N \text{ is even.} \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

Consequently, one can expect anti-phase (or close to anti-phase) ω_1 -oscillations of neighboring lasers when the stationary state becomes unstable.

2) The second solution of Eqs. (22) reads

$$\xi_{02}(\tau) = 0, \quad \eta_{02}(\tau) = \varrho_2 e^{i\omega_{21}\tau}, \quad (29)$$

where

$$\varrho_2 = \sqrt{\frac{-a_2}{b_2}}, \quad \omega_{21} = \Im m \alpha_2 + \varrho_2^2 \Im m L_2.$$

This solution, although exist at $a_2 < 0$, is unstable since $b_2 > 0$. In system (3) with corresponding parameters (point "2" in Fig. 2), one can expect bistability (coexistence) of the steady state and a non-local regime of large-amplitude oscillations.

3) The third solution of Eqs. (22) reads

$$\xi_{03}(\tau) = \rho_3 e^{i\omega_{13}\tau}, \quad \eta_{03}(\tau) = \varrho_3 e^{i\omega_{23}\tau}, \quad (30)$$

where

$$\rho_3 = \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{a_1}{b_1} - 2 \frac{a_2}{b_2} \right)}, \quad \varrho_3 = \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{a_2}{b_2} - 2 \frac{a_1}{b_1} \right)},$$

$$\omega_{13} = \Im m \alpha_1 + (\rho_3^2 + 2\varrho_3^2) \Im m L_1,$$

$$\omega_{23} = \Im m \alpha_2 + (\varrho_3^2 + 2\rho_3^2) \Im m L_2$$

This solution exists and is stable at the parameters within the sector bounded by inequalities

$$a_2 > -\frac{a_1}{2}, \quad 0 < a_1 < a_2 \frac{b_1(b_2 - 2b_1)}{b_2(2b_2 - b_1)}. \quad (31)$$

For example, such a solution exist at the parameters corresponding to point 3 in Fig. 2.

Then the functions (30) correspond to the solution of the boundary value problem (3), (4) with accuracy up to $O(\varepsilon^2)$,

$$\begin{aligned} u(t, x) &= 2\varepsilon [\rho_3 \cos \Psi_1(t, x) + \varrho_3 \cos \Psi_2(t, x)], \\ y(t, x) &= \frac{2\varepsilon}{v u_s} [\omega_1 \rho_3 \sin \Psi_1(t, x) \\ &\quad + \omega_2 \varrho_3 \sin \Psi_2(t, x)], \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

where the wave phases are $\Psi_1(t, x) = (\kappa x + \Omega_1 t)$, $\Psi_2(t, x) = (\kappa x + \Omega_2 t)$, the wave frequencies are $\Omega_1 = \omega_1 + \varepsilon^2 \omega_{13}$, $\Omega_2 = \omega_2 + \varepsilon^2 \omega_{23}$, and the wave number is $\kappa = k_{00} \varepsilon^{-1} + \theta$.

In turn, such a solution can be associated with quasiperiodic two-frequency oscillations of the radiation intensity of coupled lasers. As we have discussed before, adjacent lasers oscillate in (almost) antiphase.

4) The fourth solution of Eqs. (22) results from the Hopf bifurcation of the solution (30). The last one becomes unstable at the parameter line

$$a_1 = a_2 \frac{b_1(b_2 - 2b_1)}{b_2(2b_2 - b_1)}, \quad (33)$$

$a_1 > 0$, $a_2 < 0$, $b_1 < 0$, $b_2 > 0$. We show one of such parameters in Fig. 2, point 4. The normal form (22) is integrable. As a consequence, it has the set of solutions – circles in the phase space,

$$\xi_{04}(\tau) = \rho_4 e^{i\phi(\tau)}, \quad \eta_{04}(\tau) = \varrho_4 e^{i\psi(\tau)}, \quad (34)$$

with time-periodic amplitude, dependent on the initial conditions,

$$\rho_4(\tau) = \rho_4(\tau + 2\pi/\omega_4), \quad \varrho_4(\tau) = \varrho_4(\tau + 2\pi/\omega_4),$$

where $\omega_4 \approx O(a_{1,2})$.

Such a solution corresponds to the solution of the boundary value problem (3), (4) with accuracy up to $O(\varepsilon^2)$,

$$\begin{aligned} u(t, x) &= 2\varepsilon[\rho_4 \cos \Psi_1(t, x) + \varrho_4 \cos \Psi_2(t, x)], \\ y(t, x) &= \frac{2\varepsilon}{vu_s} [\omega_1 \rho_4 \sin \Psi_1(t, x) \\ &+ \omega_2 \varrho_4 \sin \Psi_2(t, x)], \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

where the wave phases are $\Psi_1(t, x) = (\kappa x + \omega_1 t)$, $\Psi_2(t, x) = (\kappa x + \omega_2 t)$.

The frequency ω_4 is incomparable with ω_1 and ω_2 , hence three-frequency quasiperiodic oscillations can be expected in large chain of lasers.

Remark 5. *To conclude about stability of such a three-frequency solution, it is necessary to take into account the terms of the 5-order in the quasi-normal form (20) and the normal form (22). In any case, one can expect the existence three-frequency quasiperiodic oscillations on an asymptotically long time interval.*

Remark 6. *Note, the system of Ginzburg–Landau equations (20) may have other irregular inhomogeneous solutions, for example, diffusion chaos [20, 21]. Then the solutions of the chain model can be significantly more complicated.*

6. Conclusion

We have presented a local analysis of the distributed integro-differential model with a delayed argument, which describes the dynamics of a large chain of diffusively coupled lasers. As a result of linear analysis of the distributed model, critical values of the coupling coefficient γ_0 are obtained at which the stationary state becomes unstable. The Hopf bifurcation occurs for an (asymptotically) infinite set of modes with the frequency ω_1 or ω_2 in dependence on the delay time T .

We have shown that there is also a counter set of codimension-two bifurcation points $\gamma_0 = \gamma_l(T = T_l)$, $l = 1, 2, \dots$ above which both the ω_1 -modes and the ω_2 -modes are excited. An algorithm has been proposed for reducing the initial boundary value problem to the system of equations for slowly varying amplitudes of carrier waves in such a critical case of (asymptotically) infinite dimension.

The system of two-dimensional complex Ginzburg–Landau equations with convection has been derived as a quasi-normal form. Its nonlocal dynamics determines the behavior of solutions to the original boundary value problem.

We have analyzed the simplest homogeneous periodic solutions of the quasi-normal form with parameters obtained from the initial model of coupled class-B lasers. The first stable solution corresponds to a traveling wave in the distributed original model. Such a wave can be interpreted as ω_1 -oscillations of each laser in a chain and the neighboring laser oscillates in anti-phase. The second solution, resulted in ω_2 -oscillations, is unstable. The third stable solution corresponds to the sum of two traveling waves in the distributed original model. Such waves can be interpreted as two-frequency (ω_1 and ω_2) anti-phase oscillations of lasers in the chain. At last, the fourth homogeneous solution of the quasi-normal form is possible which can result in three-frequency (ω_1 , ω_2 and ω_4) anti-phase oscillations of lasers in the chain. Additional studies of the stability of possible regimes are necessary, which would take into account the convection presented in the normalized equations.

The presented method of the quasi-normal form construction may be useful in further researches of complex laser network dynamics in other cases of diffusion or global couplings between elements.

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